

The Effect of School Facilities and Work Environment on the Performance of State Madrasah Tsanawiyah Teachers in Tapin District

Dahlia Iskandar¹, Jhoni Fahrin Sapar², Abdul Kadir³, Melania⁴, Zailani⁵

^{1,2,3,4,5} Pancasetia College of Economics Banjarmasin

ABSTRACT: The aim of this research is to determine the influence of school facilities and infrastructure as well as the work environment on the performance of State Madrasah Tsanawiyah (MTsN) teachers in Tapin Regency. This research uses quantitative methods with a correlational research type. The research population was 152 people from five MTsN throughout Tapin Regency, namely MTsN 1 Tapin, MTsN 2 Tapin, MTsN 3 Tapin, MTsN 4 Tapin, MTsN 5 Tapin and MTsN 6 Tapin. The research sample consisted of 70 people. The sampling technique in this research is simple random sampling. The data collection technique uses a questionnaire. Data were analyzed using correlation analysis and multiple regression techniques. The research results show that: (1) School Facilities and Infrastructure have a significant effect on the performance of MTsN teachers in Tapin Regency; (2) The work environment has a significant effect on the performance of MTsN teachers in Tapin Regency; (3) School facilities and infrastructure as well as the work environment simultaneously have a significant influence on the performance of MTsN teachers in Tapin Regency.

KEYWORDS: School Facilities and Infrastructures, Teacher Performance, Work Environment.

INTRODUCTION

Education is a conscious effort deliberately designed to achieve specific goals and involves personality development. According to Syafaruddin, education aims to comprehensively develop the personal potential of the younger generation. Another goal is to enhance the quality of human resources, where the low quality of education can impact the low quality of human resources. As per Law No. 20 of 2003, the government is expected to focus on developing knowledgeable, creative, and independent human resources. The importance of quality human resource education encourages the participation of all parties, especially schools or madrasahs as educational institutions. Teachers, as internal personnel, play a key role in determining the success of the school. The ability of teachers to manage classrooms and implement various teaching methods is a crucial factor in achieving school quality. Teacher performance, reflecting the ability to carry out tasks in school and in teaching activities, serves as an indicator of school success. According to Supardi, teacher performance includes the ability to carry out tasks and actions demonstrated in teaching activities.

The performance of teachers in teaching is a key factor in achieving educational goals, as teachers are the forefront of the education sector. The high or low quality of teacher performance has an impact on student achievement in school. The improvement of teacher performance in teaching is influenced by several factors, including: (1) salary, (2) facilities, (3) physical working environment conditions, and (4) leadership (Usman, 2008:464). The provision of adequate infrastructure is identified as a crucial factor in improving teacher performance in this research. Well-equipped facilities support school activities to achieve optimal results. This aligns with Bongani Kumalo's study, which concludes that participants consider resources and the availability of supporting infrastructure crucial for the maximal functioning of the learning and teaching context (Bongani, 2014).

However, there are still schools with incomplete infrastructure, and in some cases, even when facilities are complete, teachers underutilize them. As a result, teacher performance remains suboptimal, with some teachers continuing to use conventional teaching methods. Interviews with teachers in several MTsN schools in Kabupaten Tapin, including MTsN 4 Negeri Tapin, revealed inadequate or incomplete infrastructure, leading to suboptimal utilization. Teachers tend to rely more on textbooks as the primary source of teaching materials. A separate interview with a teacher from MTsN 2 Tapin on July 23, 2020, indicated that although the school's infrastructure is becoming complete, the specific utilization of facilities for learning activities is not yet fully realized. This is attributed to the time-consuming nature of using specific tools and media, coupled with the limited available teaching time, causing teachers to predominantly use textbooks in their teaching activities.

In addition to facilities and infrastructure, another factor that influences teacher performance is the work environment. According to the International Labour Office (ILO) productivity report cited in Barnawi and Arifin (2014:54), the first thing that needs to be addressed to improve teacher performance is to ensure that teachers can fulfill their duties under suitable conditions. Consequently, teachers can carry out their responsibilities without experiencing tensions, or in other words, the government must provide a conducive work environment for teachers.

The presence of a good working environment can create a conducive working relationship among individuals within it. According to Mulyasa, creating a conducive working environment requires at least two things: the teacher themselves and good relationships between teachers and parents and the surrounding community (Mulyasa, 2013:193). In line with this opinion, a supportive working condition is crucial, specifically a comfortable working environment. A favorable work environment will facilitate better performance. Individuals prefer physically safe and comfortable conditions, and most favor a relatively close working location (Usman, 2008:467). If the school's working environment is pleasant, it will stimulate teachers to fulfill their duties and responsibilities with enthusiasm and a sense of responsibility (Supardi, 2013:38). However, in practice, it often does not align with the school's expectations. An unfavorable working environment can affect individual teachers, leading to suboptimal performance in their roles as educators. This includes the physical aspects of the school environment, such as the comfort of working spaces and school facilities, as well as the psychological aspects, such as unpleasant feelings among teachers or with leadership. These factors are likely to impact a teacher's overall performance.

Based on the background described above, the problem formulations that can be derived are:

1. Is there an influence of infrastructure facilities on the performance of MTsN teachers in Tapin Regency?
2. Is there an influence of the work environment on the performance of MTsN teachers in Tapin Regency?
3. Is there a combined influence of infrastructure facilities and the work environment on the performance of MTsN teachers in Tapin Regency?

LITERATURE REVIEW

a. *School Facilities and Infrastructure*

Facilities and infrastructure are crucial aspects in enhancing the quality of a school. Teachers, as the primary drivers of the teaching and learning process, require adequate resources to make the educational experience more meaningful and achieve educational goals. According to Asiyai (2012), "The quality of education delivered by teachers and the academic achievement of pupils in any school depend on several factors, of which school facilities are paramount. School facilities are material resources that enhance teaching and learning, thereby making the process meaningful and purposeful." In line with this opinion, Margi asserts that to meet expectations in the field of education, the role of educational facilities and infrastructure is crucial, facilitating the teaching and learning process (Margi, 2015:123).

Understanding the definitions of facilities and infrastructure is essential due to their importance. According to Tatang Amirin, school facilities and infrastructure encompass all tools, equipment, or objects that can be used to facilitate (make comfortable) the implementation of education (in Utama, Kristiawanto, and Suyatmini, 2016). On the other hand, Kristiawan states that facilities are all the necessary resources in the teaching and learning process, both movable and immovable, to ensure the achievement of educational goals and smooth, effective, and efficient operations. Meanwhile, infrastructure includes all basic equipment or facilities that indirectly support the education or teaching process, such as school yards, gardens, and pathways (Kristiawan, 2017: 98). According to Mulyasa, school facilities are the equipment and supplies directly used in and supporting the educational process, especially in the teaching and learning process, such as buildings, classrooms, desks, chairs, as well as teaching aids and media. He also believes that infrastructure is the facilities indirectly supporting the smooth running of the educational process, such as school yards, gardens, school parks, and pathways to the school (Mulyasa, 2004:49).

The supporting facilities that can enhance the process of activities within an organization, including educational institutions or schools, are part of infrastructure and facilities. Effective management of infrastructure and facilities will impact the activity process. "For an organization, management is the key to success, as it greatly determines the smooth performance of the respective organization" (Arikunto 2008:2). In line with Arikunto, Baharudin states that the management of infrastructure and facilities is an

activity that involves organizing and managing educational facilities effectively and efficiently to achieve the established goals (in Kristiawan, 2017:99).

b. Work Environment

The definition of a work environment according to Nitisemito is everything around workers that can influence them in carrying out their assigned tasks (Nitisemito, 2000:183). Meanwhile, Nakpodia (2011) defines the work environment as the total conditions under which a person or a group of people works or performs their duties. Simanjuntak states that the work environment can be interpreted as the overall tools faced, the surrounding environment where a person works, the working methods, as the influence of work, both individually and as a group (2003:39). According to Sedarmayati (in Hartono, 2014:145), the work environment is the entirety of tools and materials faced, the surrounding environment where someone works, the working methods, and work arrangements, both as an individual and as a group.

Barnawi and Arifin (2014:54) add that there are several factors that affect the physical environment, including lighting, coloring, air, cleanliness, noise, and security. Sedarmayati (2011:26) explains that the non-physical environment includes all conditions related to work relationships, both with superiors and colleagues. Schools should reflect conditions that support cooperation between teachers and superiors. The conditions that should be created include a family-like atmosphere, good communication, and self-control. The creation of a good non-physical work environment can foster the creativity of teachers. According to Zhu and colleagues, "they determined that a supportive school environment, especially a supportive relationship with colleagues, encourages the innovative teaching performance of teachers" (in Balkar: 2015).

c. Teacher Performance

According to Mangkunegara (2005:9), performance is the quality and quantity of work results achieved by an employee in carrying out their duties in accordance with the responsibilities assigned to them. Gomes (in Yublina, 2015:15) defines performance as an expression related to output, efficiency, and effectiveness, often associated with productivity. Tobari defines performance as the quality and quantity of work displayed by an employee in carrying out their duties in accordance with the responsibilities given to them (Tobari, 2015:65). Susanto adds that performance is the result or achievement of an individual's or organization's work with a display that performs, describes, or produces something, whether physical or non-physical, in accordance with instructions, functions, and tasks based on knowledge, attitudes, skills, and motivation (Susanto, 2016:70).

Teachers are considered the backbone of educational success and are seen as individuals playing a crucial role in achieving educational goals, especially within the classroom. According to Jackson (2017), "Teachers are the heart of classroom instruction, so they are key to learners' productivity and hence to society's efficiency. Teachers' effectiveness depends on their competence, both academic and pedagogical, as well as a correlation between their training and skills and their position, workload, and work encouragement." Therefore, teacher performance is essential to be observed and evaluated for the advancement of the school's quality where they work. This is stipulated in Law No. 14 of 2005, Article 35, Paragraph 1, which states that teachers have the main task and workload standards, namely planning learning, implementing learning, and assessing learning outcomes.

According to Timpe, there are several factors that can influence an individual's performance, namely internal and external factors: (a) internal factors come from within the individual, such as attitudes, behaviors, and functional social skills that can affect daily work, (b) external factors come from the employee's environment, and these factors can affect the competence and motivation of functional social workers (in Tobari, 2015:70).

d. Conceptual Framework

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

e. Hypothesis

The hypothesis proposed in this research is:

- H1 : There is a significant influence of school facilities and infrastructure on the performance of MTsN teachers in Tapin Regency.
- H2 : There is a significant influence of the work environment on the performance of MTsN teachers in Tapin Regency.
- H3 : There is a significant combined influence of school facilities and infrastructure and the work environment on the performance of MTsN teachers in Tapin Regency.

RESEARCH METHOD

This research is a quantitative correlational study, examining the relationship between independent and dependent variables. The population in this study consists of MTsN in Tapin Regency, totaling 6 MTsN, namely; MTsN 1 Tapin, MTsN 2 Tapin, MTsN 3 Tapin, MTsN 4 Tapin, MTsN 5 Tapin, and MTsN 6 Tapin, with a total of 152 teachers. The sampling technique used in this research is probability sampling, employing Simple Random Sampling with the calculation based on the Slovin formula. Based on the calculation results, the determined sample size is 70 respondents/teachers. The data analysis used in this research is multiple linear regression with statistical tools facilitated by the IBM SPSS v.16 program.

RESULT

Validity Test

Table 1. The Result of Validity Test

Item	R Table	Coefficient Correlation Value					
		School Facilities and Infrastructure	Description	Work Environment	Description	Teacher Performance	Description
1	0,361	0.802	Valid	0.834	Valid	0.772	Valid
2	0,361	0.451	Valid	0.834	Valid	0.772	Valid
3	0,361	0.451	Valid	0.826	Valid	0.757	Valid
4	0,361	0.493	Valid	0.762	Valid	0.685	Valid
5	0,361	0.493	Valid	0.834	Valid	0.772	Valid
6	0,361	0.802	Valid	0.826	Valid	0.757	Valid

Item	R Table	Coefficient Correlation Value					
		School Facilities and Infrastructure	Description	Work Environment	Description	Teacher Performance	Description
7	0,361	0.801	Valid	0.387	Valid	0.772	Valid
8	0,361	0.534	Valid	0.834	Valid	0.772	Valid
9	0,361	0.457	Valid	0.826	Valid	0.757	Valid
10	0,361	0.493	Valid	0.584	Valid	0.568	Valid
11	0,361	0.557	Valid	0.557	Valid	0.539	Valid
12	0,361	0.802	Valid	0.563	Valid	0.483	Valid
13	0,361	0.451	Valid	0.471	Valid	0.534	Valid
14	0,361	0.802	Valid	0.834	Valid	0.772	Valid
15	0,361	0.801	Valid	0.387	Valid	0.483	Valid
16	0,361	0.534	Valid	0.584	Valid	0.568	Valid
17	0,361	0.557	Valid			0.539	Valid
18	0,361	0.451	Valid			0.483	Valid
19	0,361	0.534	Valid			0.757	Valid
20	0,361	0.802	Valid			0.757	Valid
21	0,361	0.485	Valid			0.483	Valid
22	0,361	0,551	Valid			0.757	Valid
23	0,361	0,568	Valid			0,757	Valid
24	0,361	0,493	Valid			0,522	Valid
25	0,361	0,38	Valid			0,757	Valid
26	0,361	0,577	Valid			0,514	Valid
27	0,361	0,493	Valid			0,483	Valid
28	0,361	0,802	Valid			0,618	Valid
29	0,361	0,577	Valid			0,455	Valid
30	0,361	0,577	Valid			0,441	Valid
31	0,361	0,493	Valid				
32	0,361	0,802	Valid				
33	0,361	0,802	Valid				
34	0,361	0,057	Valid				
35	0,361	0,493	Valid				
36	0,361	0,551	Valid				

Source: Primary data processed

Data from Table 1 above, out of 36 statements on the School Facilities and Infrastructure variable, there are 8 statements that are not valid, and 28 statement items are valid. For the Work Environment variable, out of 16 statement items, 1 statement item is proven not valid, and 15 statement items are proven to have valid values. Then, for the Teacher Performance variable, out of 30 statement items, there are 3 statements that are proven not valid, and 27 statements are declared valid because the coefficient is ≥ 0.30 .

Reliability Test

Table 2. The Result of Reliability Test

No	Variable	Cronbach's alpha	Sig	Description
1	School Facilities and Infrastructure (X1)	0,903	> 0,7	Reliable
2	Work Environment (X2)	0,854	> 0,7	Reliable
3	Teacher Performance (Y)	0,904	> 0,7	Reliable

Source: Primary data processed.

Based on Table 2 above, it is known that all variables are considered reliable. This is evidenced by the Cronbach's Alpha values being greater than the significance level (0.7)

Multiple Linear Regression

Regression analysis in this study aims to obtain hypothesis testing results regarding the influence of School Facilities and Infrastructure and Work Environment on Teacher Performance. The results of the multiple linear regression analysis in this study are as follows:

Table 3. Multiple Linear Regression Test

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.301	.530		.569	.571
	School Facilities and Infrastructure	.997	.005	.999	193.710	.000
	Work Environment	.715	.121	.583	5.923	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Teacher Performance

Source: Primary data processed.

Based on the above Table 3, the regression equation model is obtained as follows: $Y = 0,301 + 0,997X1 + 0,715X2 + \epsilon$

Based on the results of the equation above, it can be interpreted as follows:

1. The constant value (a) of positive 0.301 indicates that there is no increase in School Facilities and Infrastructure and Work Environment variables; thus, Teacher Performance is 0.301.
2. School Facilities and Infrastructure (X1) has a positive influence on Teacher Performance, with a regression coefficient of 0.997. With this positive influence, it can be interpreted that there is a positive relationship between School Facilities and Infrastructure and Teacher Performance. The coefficient value of 0.997 implies that as the School Facilities and Infrastructure variable increases, Teacher Performance will increase, assuming all other independent variables remain constant.
3. Work Environment (X2) has a positive influence on Teacher Performance, with a regression coefficient of 0.715. With this positive influence, it can be interpreted that there is a positive relationship between Work Environment and Teacher Performance. The coefficient value of 0.715 implies that as the Work Environment variable increases, Teacher Performance will increase, assuming all other independent variables remain constant.

Analysis of Coefficient of Determination

The coefficient of determination is used to determine the role of all independent variables on the value of the dependent variable, as indicated by the magnitude of the coefficient of determination (R^2). The larger its value, the better the regression equation is at estimating the dependent variable.

Table 4. Coefficient of Determination

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.999 ^a	.998	.998	0.271
a. Predictors: (Constant), School Facilities and Infrastructure, Work Environment				

Source: Primary data processed

The coefficient of determination, R Square = 0.998, signifies that 99.8% of the variance in teacher performance (Y) can be influenced by school facilities (X1) and the working environment (X2). Consequently, it can be concluded that the combined influence of school facilities and the working environment on teacher performance is 99.8%.

Hypothesis Testing

Decision-making or hypothesis testing in this research involves using the t-test (partial) and the F-test (simultaneous). The results of the partial t-test and the simultaneous F-test in this study can be seen as follows:.

1. t-Test

- a. Based on the results of hypothesis testing in Table 4, the significance level is $0.000 < 0.05$, so H_0 is rejected, and H_a is accepted. Therefore, it can be concluded that the hypothesis "there is a significant influence of School Facilities and Infrastructure on Teacher Performance" is proven.
- b. Based on the results of hypothesis testing in Table 4, the significance level is $0.000 < 0.05$, so H_0 is rejected, and H_a is accepted. Therefore, it can be concluded that the hypothesis "there is a significant influence of Work Environment on Teacher Performance" is proven.

2. F-Test

The F-Square test is conducted to assess the goodness of the model. The F-Square values of 0.02, 0.15, and 0.35 can be interpreted to determine whether the latent variable predictors have a weak, medium, or strong influence on the structural level.

Table 5. The Result of F-Test

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	2739.370	2	1369.685	1.867E4	.000 ^b
	Residual	4.915	67	0.73		
	Total	2744.286	69			
a. Dependent Variable: Teacher Performance						
b. Predictors: (Constant), School Facilities and Infrastructure, Work Environment						

Source: Primary data processed.

Based on Table 5 above, the Hypothesis Testing indicates a significance level of $0.000 < 0.05$, thus rejecting H_0 and accepting H_a . Based on the calculations above, it can be concluded that the hypothesis stating "there is a significant simultaneous influence of School Facilities and Infrastructure and Work Environment on Teacher Performance" is proven.

DISCUSSION

The Influence of School Facilities on Teacher Performance

The research results indicate that school facilities significantly influence the performance of MTsN teachers in Tapin Regency by 99.8%. The better the school facilities, the better the teacher performance.

In the previous discussion, many theories mentioned factors that support teacher performance in learning, one of which is school facilities. With adequate school facilities, teachers are assisted in conducting diverse, interesting, and meaningful learning activities. This aligns with the findings of Fauziana (2017), stating a significant influence of school facilities on teacher performance by 25.4%.

Complete school facilities will encourage and motivate teachers in conducting teaching and learning activities, enabling them to enhance their abilities in making their teaching more engaging and optimal. Teachers equipped with adequate school facilities demonstrate better performance compared to those lacking proper facilities.

The Influence of the Working Environment on Teacher Performance

Based on the results of hypothesis testing 2, it is known that the working environment significantly influences teacher performance, as indicated by the t-test result with a t-value of $135.990 > t\text{-table}$. At a significance level of 0.05 with a coefficient of determination of 0.34, it can be concluded that teacher performance is influenced by the working environment by 34%. The research findings suggest that the working environment has a positive influence on teacher performance. A favorable working environment makes teachers feel secure and comfortable in carrying out teaching activities, enabling them to enhance the quality of their teaching. The school's working environment reflects the physical and non-physical working conditions that can impact teachers in performing their roles as educators.

This is supported by earlier research by Hartono (2014), indicating a significant influence between the working environment and teacher performance, leading to the conclusion that the working environment has a confirmed and tested impact on teacher performance.

The Combined Influence of School Facilities and Working Environment on Teacher Performance

The research findings indicate that school facilities and the working environment together have a significant impact on the performance of MTsN teachers in Tapin Regency, amounting to 99.8%. From these findings, it can be interpreted that school facilities and the working environment, when considered together, possess a substantial influence on teacher performance. Complete school facilities will encourage and motivate teachers in conducting teaching and learning activities, enabling them to enhance their capabilities in organizing instructional activities. Similarly, the creation of a positive working environment can improve the performance of teachers. The results of this research align with a study conducted by Handayani (2004). Therefore, it can be concluded that the influence of education level, school facilities, and the working environment on teacher performance is accepted and tested for its validity.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the research and discussion, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. There is a significant influence of school facilities on the performance of MTsN teachers in Tapin Regency.
2. There is a significant influence of the working environment on the performance of MTsN teachers in Tapin Regency.
3. There is a significant combined influence of school facilities and the working environment on the performance of MTsN teachers in Tapin Regency.

RECOMMENDATION

Based on the results of the discussion and conclusions, the recommendations from the results of this research are:

1. The infrastructure at MTsN in Tapin Regency is already quite adequate; however, its management and utilization are not yet optimal. The researcher suggests that the entire school community collaboratively manage and utilize these facilities to support learning activities. Addressing infrastructure issues is crucial and should be taken seriously, as it significantly affects the smoothness of the teaching and learning process. Proper facilities and optimal utilization in learning activities can enhance the quality of education.
2. In this study, the influence of the working environment on the performance of MTsN teachers in Tapin Regency is only 34%, indicating that only a small portion of the working environment indicators can improve teacher performance. This not only includes relationships with superiors and colleagues but also encompasses the overall conditions of the school, both directly and indirectly.
3. With the existing theories, the results of this research can be further developed by other researchers to improve or refine this study. Additionally, they can explore and examine other variables related to the improvement of teacher performance and the factors influencing it.

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